

HortiMED

Towards circular horticulture: closing the loop on Mediterranean greenhouses

The PRIMA programme is supported under Horizon 2020 the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.

Using smart technologies in Integrated agriculture – aquaculture (IAA) systems

Prof. Ashraf Mohamed Abdelsamee' Goda
National Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries (NIOF), Cairo, Egypt

Expansion Prospects of Integrated Agriculture-Aquaculture in Arid areas

WorldFish, 08 August 2022, Abbassa, Abu Hammad, Sharkia, Egypt

HortiMED is part of PRIMA programme supported by the European Union. The PRIMA programme is supported under Horizon 2020 the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. HortiMED has received funding under the Grant Agreement Number 1915.

Outline

Introduction

Overview of HortiMED project

Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA)

Aquaponics

Smart Aquaculture-Aquaponics system using Internet of Things (IOT)

Automated Monitoring and Control System (AMCS)

Expected Outcomes

Introduction

Human
Population

7.7 billion
Day by day
Food demand

Yields

2050

Climatic and other stress
Factors.

Food
products,
crop and
fish

Produce food
Sustainable

Rich source

Essential

Micronutrients

Consumer's diet

Fish

Poor

Underdeveloped

Introduction

Farmer

Water resources

Sudden climate change

Influence of intensive aquaculture system on aquatic environment

Effect of crops protection using pesticide

Unsuitable management technique

Water quality

No government interest

Traditional aquaculture system

Aquaculture is a promising source to fill gap between of food supply and demand.

Introduction

Traditional water quality monitoring cannot change the dynamic of aquaculture water quality monitoring and also achieved a fixed point monitoring. Farmers need real time and accurate information to monitor and maximize production potential.

Nowadays Smart aquaculture (Intelligence and Automation) is one of the sustainable development trends for the aquaculture industry to enhance aquaculture production, and be friendly to the environment.

Introduction

An Internet of Things (IoT) based smart aquaculture model to in real-time monitor and control aquaculture water quality (pH, water DO level, temperature, turbidity and motion detection of fish) ensures survival of aquatic life, the quality of growth and increases the economic benefits of aquaculture.

Introduction

The integration of aquatic animal and horticultural production (IAA) through hydroponics as known aquaponics system, in a synergetic environment, a real sustainable solution to optimize the reuse of nutrient and water resources.

Introduction

One of the most innovative solutions is to design and build a smart and sustainable integrated system in order to ensure the safe supply of water resources, control the quality over time and that will be able to grow a large amount of food in a limited space.

Overview of HortiMED project

The present work, conducted in the frame of HortiMED H2020 PRIMA Project (Grant Number 1915) funded by the European Union, was aimed at evaluating the feasibility of combining Integrated MultiTrophic Aquaculture (IMTA, production of different aquatic species, tilapia, grey mullet, crayfish, clams and silver carp) with horticultural production using Floating Raft System (FRS) and Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) as hydroponic systems to production different horticultural crops (red and green leaf lettuce, chili pepper, cucumber, eggplant, tomato, mallow, bell pepper, watercress and celery) to maximize nutrient cycling resulting from culturing plants and aquatic animals.

Overview of HortiMED project

CONSORTIM

Coordinator

INKOA SISTEMAS S.L. (INKOA)
Ribera de Axpe 11 Edificio D1 Dpto. 208
48950 Erandio SPAIN
www.inkoa.com

Partners

National Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries (NIOF)
<http://www.niof.sci.eg/>

University of Mohamed Khider
Biskra (UMKB)
<http://univ-biskra.dz/index.php/en/>

Universidad de Deusto (UDEUSTO)
<http://consumerupdate.org/>

Overview of HortiMED project

Overall objective

To provide the Mediterranean horticultural community with **innovative tools to enable resource efficient year round greenhouse cultivation** by harnessing the potential of both **simple and advanced technologies for smart nutrient, irrigation & climate control**, and integrated pest management taking into account their feasibility and cost-effectiveness at individual greenhouse level.

Specific objectives

To develop and test a user-friendly and flexible Decision Support System (DSS) allowing smart nutrient, irrigation & climate control, and integrated pest management in greenhouses through:

- Expert advisory services to help farmers in intensive knowledge tasks where climatic, crop and nutrient variables decisively influence crop growth and productivity (precise water & fertilisers' needs, efficient climate control...)
- Efficient and cost-effective partial or full automation of greenhouses (fertigation, ventilation, heating, etc.)

Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA)

Nutrient budget (g / kg fish)

From dietary 101.7 g nitrogen (N) and 15.9 g phosphorous (P), about 28 % of (N) and 25 % of (P) added through feed are incorporated in the fish body. 8% of N and 45% of P will sediment as feces and uneaten feed pellets. From fish excretion and dissolution of fresh feed pellets, 64 % of N and 30 % of P are directly released as dissolved nutrients into the water.

What is IMTA?

Integrated Multi-trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) is based on the **Ecosystem Carrying Capacity** of an area, where species from different trophic levels are cultivated in a way that produces more food (in which the by-products (wastes) from one species are recycled to become inputs for another) and increases incomes, while ensuring generated nutrients are recycled naturally.

NUTRIENT CYCLING- Once the fish feed is added to the system, a substantial part used for growth and the remaining part, excreted as soluble and solid faeces. Uneaten feed, faeces and soluble excretions are recaptured by the subsequent extractive aquatic species (i.e. mullet, crayfish, clams and silver carp) which use them as nourishment, acting as living filters. Besides, the last pond acts as a mechanical filter where a significant part of the solid wastes is captured.

Aquaponics

The biological wastes excreted by fish (ammonia, salts) and those generated from the microbial breakdown of feed for fish (nitrite and nitrate) are absorbed by plants as nutrients for growth.

Nitrate (NO_3^-) and orthophosphate (H_2PO_4^- , HPO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-}) are absorbed by plants' roots, cleaning the water for fish

Partial fertilization (K, Mg, Fe)

Bacteria convert fish waste (NH_3 , NO_2^-) into fertilizer (NO_3^-) for plants

Only fed species
Tilapia (finfish)

Extractive species use the organic particulate nutrients (uneaten feed & faeces) for nourishment, acting as living filters

Biological filter

Smart Aquaculture-Aquaponics system using Internet of Things (IOT)

Smart Aquaculture-Aquaponics system using Internet of Things (IoT)

Smart Aquaculture system using Internet of Things (IOT)

IoT system (WiFish from ReNile)

11 sensing nodes to measure pH, DO, EC, T_{water} , T_{air} , RH and TDS.

Offline sensors

soil moisture, soil pH and light intensity

Water sampling and laboratory analysis

1. Weekly monitoring of N & P compounds
2. Biweekly monitoring of physicochemical parameters, major cations and major anions
3. Monthly monitoring of trace metals

HortiMED FieldBook APP

Data of offline sensors, laboratory analysis, crop & aquatic species growth

Smart Aquaculture system using Internet of Things (IoT)

PRIMA Full Proposal HortiMED
July 2019

Figure 2. IoT system architecture

Mobile application

Web application

AUTOMATED MONITORING AND CONTROL SYSTEM

AMCS Design → 27 Requirements (R)

ID	Short name	Priority	Description
R1	Greenhouse systems' automation	Must Have	The AMCS should be capable of automating greenhouse systems (e.g. aeration, air renewal, artificial lighting, etc.) based on current greenhouse conditions.
R2	24x7 (continuous)	Must have	The AMCS should be able to run constantly without disruption or downtime, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.
R3	Offline mode availability	Must have	The AMCS should be able to work without internet connection.
R4	Easiness of use	Must have	No specific technical knowledge is needed for the use of the AMCS (user interface).
R5	Scalability	Must Have	The AMCS capabilities should be easily increased, to be able to cope as demands increase, either in terms of the number of systems to be automated by the AMCS or in terms of the number of sensors/monitoring systems to be connected to the AMCS. The scalable nature of the AMCS should also allow for progressive investments to end-user with low investment capacity.
R6	Cost-effective	Must have	The AMCS should target low cost and readily available components as much as possible to deliver a cost reasonable AMCS that can be afforded by greenhouse managers with low investment capacity.

Automated Monitoring and Control System (AMCS)

CROP YIELD AND TOTAL PRODUCTION

IMTA-Floating Raft System

Crop	Transplanting date	Harvesting date	Area (m ²)	Total production (kg)	Yield (kg/m ²)
Chilli pepper	23 May 2021	24 September 2021	18	32.67	1.82
Cucumber	23 May 2021	31 July 2021	15	255.70	17.05
Bell pepper	30 May 2021	11 September 2021	9	9.39	1.04
Eggplant	15 June 2021	23 October 2021	6	3.50	0.58
Celery	18 July 2021	30 November 2021	3	4.50	1.50
Green leaf lettuce	18 July 2021	3 September 2021	18	28.79	1.60
Red leaf lettuce	18 July 2021	3 September 2021	18	24.64	1.37

IMTA-Traditional Soil Culture

Crop	Transplanting date	Harvesting date	Area (m ²)	Total production (kg)	Yield (kg/m ²)
Chilli pepper	23 May 2021	24 September 2021	80	227.61	2.85
Bell pepper	30 May 2021	1 October 2021	20	55.80	2.79
Eggplant	15 June 2021	13 October 2021	6	29.50	4.92
Mallow	13 July 2021	10 November 2021	8	45.00	5.63
Watercress	13 July 2021	30 November 2021	8	18.50	2.31
Celery	18 July 2021	30 November 2021	3	6.00	2.00

IMTA-Nutrient Film Technique

Crop	Transplanting date	Harvesting date	Area (m ²)	Total production (kg)	Yield (kg/m ²)
Green leaf lettuce	18 July 2021	3 September 2021	9	21.15	2.35
Red leaf lettuce	18 July 2021	3 September 2021	9	18.54	2.06

CROP YIELD AND TOTAL PRODUCTION

CROP YIELD AND TOTAL PRODUCTION

AQUATIC BIOMASS PRODUCTION

	Nile tilapia	Grey mullet	Crayfish	Clams	Silver carp	Total
Initial biomass (kg)	13.5	0.57	2.67	37.07	2.37	56.18
Gain (kg/cycle)	112.73	17.66	2.13	28.1	19.22	179.84
Final biomass (kg)	126.23	18.23	4.8	65.16	21.59	236.01

FEED CONVERSION RATIO

Nile tilapia is the only species fed (273.88kg feed/cycle).

The remaining aquatic species use as food source the wastes from the previous aquatic species.

The cumulative apparent FCR value of the system is 1.52

CUMULATIVE FCR FOR THE SYSTEM

RESOURCE EFFICIENCY

Nutrient Use Efficiency (NUE)

Only partial fertilization to prevent deficiencies

Total fertilizer consumption: 11.18 kg/cycle

NUE: 1.86236×10^{-5} kg fertilizer/m² /kg produced

Water Use Efficiency (WUE)

Water evaporation 29.35m³/week

Plant transpiration 3.22 m³/week

Total water consumption: 880.60 m³/cycle

WUE: 0.001467 m³ water/m² greenhouse/kg produced

CONCLUSIONS

In HortiMED IMTA-aquaponics system **significant improvements** have been recorded in **NUE and WUE, net aquatic biomass production and FCR**, compared to traditional horticulture or aquatic monoculture systems. These results indicates that **IMTA-aquaponics as a bio-integrated food production system is not only a successful method for the simultaneous crop and aquatic biomass production, but also a suitable strategy for cycling nutrients and water.**

HortiMED will continue with the IMTA-aquaponics research in the experimental site during at least two production cycles, including: (i) the N and P balance for fish-culture ponds and different experimental hydroponic systems; (ii) optimizing plant crop yields for greenhouse vegetables and evaluating the production of other crop species (e.g. tomato and broccoli); and (iii) determining critical water quality parameters in the system to achieve optimal conditions for both fish and plants.

THANK YOU

شكرا **Shukraan**

Merci Gracias

Eskerrik asko

HortiMED Project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The contents of this document are the sole responsibility of the consortium the PRIMA Foundation is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.